

A Implementation of dynamic replication method

Algorithm 1: Dynamic replication

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1 For each job, executed in site  $j$  with local SE  $s$ , to download file  $f$ 
2
3 Timeout = PatientTime =  $\frac{FileSize}{min\_bandwidth}$ , Time = 0,
4 Lock = False, Nb_retry = 3, Retry_freq = 2s
5 Flag = Check whether  $F$  exists in  $S$ ;
6 if Flag then
7   | download  $f$  from  $S$ 
8 else
9   if Lock then
10    | while  $Time < PatientTime$  do
11      | sleep(Retry_freq) ;
12      | retry Flag ;
13      | Time += Retry_freq ;
14    | end
15    | if ! Flag then
16      | use EGI's service to download file (lcg-cp);
17    | else
18      | download  $f$  from local SE  $s$ 
19    | end
20  | else
21    | Lock = True;
22    | Locked:
23    |  $i = 0$ ;
24    | Sorted_list = Sort all replicas of  $f$  by rules as lcg-cp ;
25    | while  $i < Nb\_retry$  and  $status == Fail$  do
26      | status = download  $f$  from Sorted_list[ $i$ ] with Timeout ;
27      |  $i ++$  ;
28    | end
29    | if  $status == Success$  then
30      | register  $f$  onto  $s$ 
31    | else
32      | use EGI's service to download file (lcg-cp);
33    | end
34    | Unlock
35  | end
36 end
37
```
